

Formation of Managerial Skills of Students in the Process of Practical Training

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Annotation: In recent years, a new educational paradigm has been formed, within which the quality of modern education will be determined by the extent to which graduates of the technical school have developed competencies - the ability to identify links between knowledge and situations and apply knowledge adequately to the problems being solved. A competitive personality must have many developed qualities, such as independence, organization, the ability to solve creative tasks, design their own activities, be ready for accelerated adaptation, changes in production and social space. Therefore, one of the important forms and methods of implementing new approaches in the educational process is competence-based learning technologies.

Keywords: Competence, Improvement of the structure, Competence-based system, Subject-oriented tasks, qualification tasks, professional tasks.

Competence is an important characteristic of the readiness of trainees and one of the main requirements for the training of specialists in a technical school. Competence is not only an in-depth knowledge of the discipline, the state of adequate task performance, the ability to perform relevant activities, but also competence involves constant updating of knowledge, mastering new information for successful application in specific conditions, potential readiness to solve professional tasks with knowledge.

At a time when the economy lives in the mode of periodic technological and organizational renewal, continuous improvement of production methods and management principles, completely new requirements are imposed on the employee. Employers prefer creatively active people who possess advanced technologies and are able to practically apply their knowledge. The ability to ensure high quality of products that are rapidly changing in their characteristics and technologically increasingly complex, to keep the cost of products low by constantly improving production methods, the desire to improve and expand their knowledge, the ability to constantly learn is appreciated.

The Federal State Educational Standard of the third generation pays special attention to the competencies that students should master. In this regard, such priorities of the individual as social activity, free orientation in the surrounding society, possession of information technologies, tolerance towards others and the ability to continue education throughout life come to the fore. The competence-oriented educational process allows students to develop the ability to make an informed choice from several options for the development of events, to resolve problematic situations of both applied and abstract nature, to make responsible decisions.

The improvement of the structure and content of training specialists based on a competence-based approach has been considered quite intensively in recent years.

Insufficient theoretical elaboration of the formulated problem and its great practical significance prompted us to turn to this topic ("Formation of managerial skills of students in the process of practical training").

Objective: to improve the quality of students' training by forming managerial competence in their learning process.

We believe that the quality of specialist training can be improved if:

- one of the main components of the competence of a future specialist is considered managerial competence, which entails the need to determine its essence;
- the theoretical and methodological foundations of the model of formation of managerial competence among students are revealed;
- when developing the goals, content and technology of training, use a competence-oriented approach that allows you to form in-demand key and professional competencies of future specialists who are ready to implement a new educational paradigm of "Lifelong Learning";
- to form managerial competence, use a model of contextual learning, in which the latest achievements of managerial theory and modular interdisciplinary complexes are included in the content and technology of training, the self-assessment method is used as a mechanism for developing the student's potential for self-management, self-development and active use of reflexive technologies, system diagnostics of the formation of managerial competencies based on B.Bloom's taxonomy is carried out. (American scientist B. Bloom. B.Bloom's taxonomy of learning goals has 6 levels: knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation).
- American experts identify eight main groups of specialist qualities that make up management skills:
 - the ability to communicate on a formal and informal basis and effectively interact with colleagues who are equal in position;
 - the ability to show the qualities of a leader necessary in communicating with subordinates;
 - ability to navigate conflict situations and resolve them correctly;
 - the ability to receive and process the necessary information, evaluate, compare, assimilate it;
 - ability to make decisions in uncertain situations;
 - the ability to manage their time, distribute work among subordinates, give them the necessary authority, promptly make organizational decisions;
 - the ability to demonstrate the business qualities of an entrepreneur: to set promising goals, use favorable opportunities, change the organizational structure of the enterprise in time,
 - The ability to critically assess the likely consequences of their decisions, learn from their mistakes.

To form these qualities in the learning process, it is necessary to model the control systems included in the structure of specific socio-economic systems. Accordingly, there is a need for teaching methods based on models of two subsystems of the control system: a model of a communication system and a model of a system of joint activity. Such methods are role-playing and imitation games.

The process of forming a managerial culture among students requires a systematic approach. We are implementing a system of management culture formation by means of professional disciplines.

Teachers of special disciplines use a business game for the purposes of training future specialists (e.g., teachers of economic disciplines: "Forms and systems of remuneration", "My Homeland", "Stock Exchange", etc.) Moreover, this game form can be considered as a professional module that

allows a student to master the professional competencies necessary for a specialist, and to show them in conditions that mimic professional activity. It allows you to develop:

- skills of free use of accumulated theoretical knowledge, as well as professional practical experience;
- skills of understanding professional problems and finding approaches to their solution;
- The ability to use existing knowledge independently or in a team to solve problem situations in conditions that simulate professional activity.

In addition, the game activates the mental activity of students, directs their creative potential to solve professional situations, promotes adaptation to the future profession, since students are faced with a common task that requires the use of professional competencies. The use of business games allows you to identify and trace the peculiarities of the psychology of participants. Therefore, business games are often used in the personnel selection process. With their help, you can determine:

- the level of business activity of a candidate for a particular position;
- the presence of tactical and (or) strategic thinking;
- speed of adaptation in new conditions;
- the ability to analyze the capabilities and motives of other people and influence their behavior;
- leadership style, orientation when making decisions to play "for yourself" or "in the interests of the team" and many other

Business games allow you to get a more or less clear idea of how a person will behave in a team, which is very important for a manager.

An analysis of the experience of using this form of training has shown that during the business game, students along with professional ones form cross-cutting competencies. They acquire the ability to effectively interact with colleagues, managers, clients, using various means of communication.

The system we are considering is determined by the social order for specialists with managerial culture, therefore, the formation of managerial culture acts as a specific goal of the system we propose.

When developing tasks, we take into account the following requirements:

- the set of tasks and tasks should not be random, but should be a system;
- when building a system of tasks and tasks, it is necessary to take into account both the age characteristics of students and the specifics of the communicative situations in which they most often find themselves;
- each task should be related to the previous one and be built on the basis of increasing complexity from reproductive to creative;
- the system of tasks and tasks should not only contribute to the acquisition of communicative knowledge and skills, but also contribute to their transfer to new conditions, activating the communicative abilities and information needs of the student;
- tasks should contribute to the development of motivational, orientation and volitional qualities of the individual, the processes of self-regulation, self-knowledge and reflection;
- That is, the preparation process includes three significantly different components:
- mastering universal forms of activity for solving managerial tasks and problems;
- familiarization with the value system of culture that generates the goals and criteria of this activity;

- Gaining knowledge about the subject of solving problems of personal development.

All elements of the formation system are combined into one whole through a variety of interdisciplinary connections.

The system of formation of managerial culture formed by us is considered as a factor of improving the quality of professional training of a future specialist.

We determine the quality of the level of managerial culture by the following criteria:

- Quality is the conformity of the subject as a result of professional training to the state standard of secondary vocational education.
- The qualitative state of knowledge is not constant, it changes as its new properties are revealed.
- The quality of students' knowledge is not something unchangeable, since its main indicators depend on the organization of the learning process, the individual characteristics of students.

The practical value of the system depends on how fully the basic requirements and necessary qualities imposed on the future specialist will be reflected.

Subject-oriented tasks act as a means of forming students' knowledge in academic disciplines (modules) of the professional cycle, necessary and sufficient for mastering the skills and abilities of a specialist as part of specific professional competencies, the development of students' cognitive activity. Such tasks are based on the consideration of production situations aimed at the assimilation by students of knowledge on the topics (sections) of the discipline (module), the ability to apply them. They are offered to students in the form of an oral or test assignment, in the form of practical or laboratory work. At the same time, the proposed tasks may contain a scientific contradiction presented in the form of a cognitive problem and thereby contribute to the acquisition of creative or emotional-value experience by students.

Practice-oriented tasks act as a means of forming students' system of integrated skills and abilities necessary for mastering professional competencies of a specialist. Such tasks are constructed by selecting production situations in which the skills and abilities of students in academic disciplines (modules) of the professional cycle are a necessary condition for preparing students to solve professional tasks within the competence of a specialist. Depending on the specific professional tasks of the production activity, practice-oriented tasks can be constructed:

- based on the selection of situations that ensure the development of technological aspects of production activities that require the use of special skills and abilities specific to this profession and specialty;
- based on the creation of production activity situations in which, along with the actual technological ones, the problems of organizing activities, choosing its optimal structure, and issues of managing production activities are posed;
- Based on the creation of personality-oriented situations that require the student to be able to find non-standard ways to solve production issues, a reasonable choice of a particular position in production activities or industrial relations, overcoming moral contradictions, making decisions on the choice and correction of ways to improve the quality of work.

Depending on the degree of coverage of the subject areas of knowledge, practice-oriented tasks can be disciplinary, interdisciplinary and meta-disciplinary. Such tasks can be offered to students in the form of a laboratory or practical task.

Practice-oriented tasks act as a means of forming students' system of integrated skills and abilities necessary for mastering professional competencies of a specialist.

Professional tasks act as a means of forming students' skills to identify, develop and apply optimal methods for solving professional tasks by types and levels of industrial activity.

These tasks are based on the consideration of situations arising at various levels of production activities, and are formulated in the form of production tasks (assignments). The algorithm for solving professional tasks should provide for a logically completed procedure of actions that ensures the fulfillment of tasks (assignments) at the appropriate level of implementation of production activities: operational, functional, qualification.

Depending on the types of future production activities, professional tasks may be focused on solving technological, organizational, managerial and other issues, and the procedure for their implementation may be reproductive or problem-searching in nature. According to the degree of coverage of subject areas of knowledge, such tasks may have a disciplinary or interdisciplinary nature, and according to the level of implementation of production activities, they may be qualification, functional or operational:

- Qualification tasks are developed based on the requirements of the educational standard for the main types of specialist activities, cover the content of one or more professional modules and serve to develop functional and operational professional tasks. These tasks can be offered to graduates in the form of a final qualifying work assignment. The application of this type of tasks is necessary for mastering the qualification professional competencies of a specialist;
- Functional tasks are developed on the basis of the content of academic disciplines (modules) involved in the formation of professional competencies at the level of specialist functions. They are offered to students in a practical lesson or course design. The application of this type of tasks is necessary for the development of functional professional competencies of a specialist;
- Operational tasks are developed on the basis of the content of academic disciplines (modules) involved in the formation of professional competencies of a specialist at the level of a production operation. They are offered to students at a practical or seminar class. The application of this type of tasks is necessary for the development of operational professional competencies.

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